

EFFICIENT TRANSFER OF PROMISING RESEARCH RESULTS TO INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS USING ADAPTIVE PROCESSES

Jan Bremer¹, Dr. Claus Bremer¹

¹BCT GmbH

Carlo-Schmid-Allee 3, 44263 Dortmund, Germany

Email: info@bct-online.de, web page: <http://www.bct-online.de>

Keywords: Adaptive machining, knowledge transfer, research to industry, composite repair, automation

ABSTRACT

Key aspect to successful transfer of research results to an industrial application is often the automation of a newly developed process. Especially for applications in the aerospace, energy and automotive sectors, but also in many other applications, complex shapes and high performance requirements characterize many components.

Technological improvements in these fields hence often push the boundaries of what is possible in engineering. But with cost also being a very important factor, even the most advanced processes must be economically feasible. Fulfilling all requirements towards quality as well as cost can often only be achieved through automation. To make a transfer of advanced research to an industrial scale possible, the often complex and precise processes with a multitude of parameters must hence be automated at an early stage. With additional factors such as thermal warp from manufacturing processes or wear and tear in MRO (maintenance, repair and overhaul) coming into play in an operational environment, automation with standard NC programs is often not feasible.

Adaptive processes are a key enabler to the automation of such processes. By gathering information on the actual component to be processed, individually adapted NC programs as well as process parameter control can be used to achieve a stable process. This can greatly accelerate the transfer from laboratory testing into an operational environment, or even enable it at all.

An inherent scalability of adaptive processes offers benefits from knowledge transfer to full-scale industrial applications, helping bridge the so-called “Valley of Death” on the TRL (technology readiness level) scale and bringing more promising research to industrial applications faster.

1 INTRODUCTION

Many research results, both in industry and academia, show great promise. However, a second major obstacle is often faced after completion of a successful research project: Transfer to an industrial application. The phenomenon of many projects facing major delays or even complete discontinuation at this stage is often referred to as the “Valley of death”.

This level of technology transfer is characterized by moving from a laboratory scale and environment to demonstration and a prototype in an operational environment. A key challenge for many processes to face when transferring to components from an operational environment is process stability. Especially for processes involving controlled movements along a component, for example additive processes such as laser cladding or subtractive processes such as milling or grinding, both absolute precision as well as precision relative to the actual part are highly important to achieve process quality and stability. In a laboratory scale on controlled test specimens absolute precision usually equates to precision relative to the part, as standardized geometries are used and specimens are often flat and even.

The stage of technology demonstration in operational environments and tests of first prototypes in such environments pose a different challenge. A process which has shown great stability in laboratory testing might require the same high precision relative to the part as on test specimens, but components

in an operational environment are exposed to a whole array of influencing factors which are detrimental to their consistency and precision. In order to transfer the possibly achieved improvements from test specimens to actual components, it must hence be made possible to offset for factors such as imprecise clamping, wear and tear and other deviations from nominal properties and geometry.

Adaptive machining, preferably in combination with in-machine scanning, permits for such factors to be considered and offset automatically, regaining process stability and precision by creating a customized NC program for every individual part. As well-designed adaptive processes can scale very well, both in regard to part size and count, they can also accelerate even further development into a final industrial application.

Hence Adaptive processes are a very powerful tool to enable researchers and industry alike to accelerate the transfer of research results into an industrial application and to help bridge the so-called “Valley of Death” throughout that process.

An overview of the principles of adaptive processes shall be given and different technologies used in composite applications will be presented.

2 BASICS OF ADAPTIVE MACHINING

2.1 Geometry capture

The starting point of every adaptive machining process is knowledge of component geometry. Hence a precise measuring process lies at the core of the adaptive milling process.

Different technologies can be utilized for the capture of component position and geometry, each offering different benefits and drawbacks. A second important aspect is the decision as to whether geometrical data capture should be integrated into the NC machine or whether a separate scanning system would be more advantageous. If separate units are used for scanning and for NC machining, additional expenses and effort may be required for materials handling and possibly for fixtures and component referencing as well.

In general, machine-integrated scanning is the preferred system configuration.

2.2 Optical scanning on NC machine tools

While an overwhelming variety of scanning technologies is available for separate scanning units, the possibilities for machine-integrated geometrical data capture are currently limited largely to touch trigger probes.

To remedy this situation, a solution has been developed that permits 6-axis scanning with line scanners in 5-axis NC machines. Here the spindle is used as the sixth controlled axis. With this solution process-integrated and machine-integrated scanning of components can be realized

2.2 Adaptation of NC programs and process parameters

The scanning data gathered in previous process steps is the base for adaptive processing of the component. First a 3D surface model, reproducing the actual geometry of the damaged area, is generated from the scan data. For this, a nominal CAD geometry may be taken into account, but is not needed.

To create the individually adapted NC program for the actual part, a so-called master milling program is calculated initially. This master program is based on the nominal geometry of the component or as a 2.5D-milling program in a plane. The master program is similar to a program which would be used in testing on laboratory specimens or components without individual deviations. Hence it can be derived from existing process parameters and programs from testing with little effort.

Based on this nominal NC program and the surface model calculated from the captured geometry the actual adaptive program is then calculated.

As this process is fully automated it is now possible to run a NC program which is only based on a nominal geometry on actual parts with deviations from this geometry with high precision and short cycle times.

Added benefit of precise knowledge of the actual part as well as an individually calculated program is that process parameters can also be linked to the adaptation process, allowing control over these parameters according to the part in hand. This means that even sensitive processes can be run in a stable manner in an operational environment.

3 COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS

Applications with composite materials face a unique set of challenges. Shape deviations play a decisive role in many processes during manufacturing as well as maintenance, repair and overhaul.

This makes geometrically adaptive processes a suitable solution to automate steps which are currently being executed manually. Especially during repair processes and when joining composite components high precision and reproducible surface quality is required to permit structural bonding.

A solution for automated adaptive machining was developed and successfully tested. In the following different examples of challenges faced will be shown and the according solutions shall be presented.

3.1 Machining unknown geometries

As the laser line scanner has a relatively small focus area, a precise distance to the surface to be scanned must be maintained in order to achieve precise measurements. To achieve this, a rough geometrical model of the component is needed to generate the scanning path.

A point laser is used to detect the topology of the area, from which the adaptive milling software calculates a tool path for the laser line scanner. In a next step the line scanner is used to detect the 3D geometry of the component with a high degree of accuracy.

3.2 Hard-to-scan materials

To furthermore enhance accuracy and data reliability from the scanning process, a method was developed to compensate for the influence of optical properties of the scanned surface. To achieve this, an algorithm calculates multiple passes for the laser line scanner of the same surface, but from different angles. Through the input of multiple data points of the same surface the algorithm can then calculate the influence of the surface properties and compensate for them. Additionally, this scanning method allows for a consistency check of the gathered data to prevent damage to the component through errors in the scanning data.

For easy-to-scan surfaces, a red-light laser line scanner is used. This scanning equipment is sufficient for most CFRP applications. For fully automated operation using tool-changing capabilities, a wireless version is used. For more difficult-to-scan surfaces, an enhanced blue-light laser line scanner is preferable. This scanning method has shown greatly improved scanning precision compared to a red light laser scanner on semi-transparent surfaces such as GFRP.

3.3 Surface activation for bonding

The surface properties of a FRP component are crucial to allow structural bonding and ensure sufficient mechanical properties. Many different technologies have been developed and used to improve bonding conditions. While mechanical processes such as milling are perfectly suited to remove large amounts of material efficiently as well as provide a mechanically suitable surface for bonding, the chemical properties of the achieved surface are not ideal for this purpose. Advantageous processes for chemical surface preparation are for example plasma or UV treatment. Hence a combination of milling for material removal and plasma processes for surface activation are considered ideal for reliable bonded repairs. [1].

Tests have been conducted successfully to integrate atmospheric plasma after the milling process to ensure ideal bonding conditions.

The treatment process itself was realized utilizing a machine-held plasma device which was mounted instead of a tool. The process is controlled similarly to a milling process, where the plasma is guided in a controlled distance to the actual part at a controlled speed.

3.3 Scarf geometry generation

In applications where adaptive machining is used for repair preparation, the optimal scarf geometry is always dependent on parameters such as mechanical loads, ply layup, materials and more. Hence the geometry and its parameters need to be adjusted, and then in addition to the actual part geometry.

To facilitate quick programming of a scarfing application, a scarfing geometry generator was generated, which automatically generates a master milling program with the input of some geometrical parameters that can be used in a subsequent adaptation process.

The scarfing geometry generator in combination with the above described measuring and adaptation processes permits scarfing of almost all geometries and component sizes, assuming a suitable machine tool is available.

This illustrates how an adaptive process, once implemented, can be used from a test specimen scale and be transferred with little effort to an operational environment for testing and then for operation.

6 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The NC code in examples shown is based on calculations which have no inherent limit other than the machine tool used. This illustrates how an adaptive process, once implemented, can be used from a test specimen scale and be transferred with little effort to an operational environment for testing and then for operation.

The possibility of also controlling different process parameters allows this concept to be transferred to many different applications and technologies.

Hence it can be concluded that adaptive processes are a powerful tool to aid in transferring promising research from laboratory scale to industrial testing and applications by permitting processes to be run with high precision and controlled process parameters even on components with deviations from nominal shapes as often encountered in an operational environment.

REFERENCES

- [1] Holtmannspötter, J., von Czarnecki, J, Feucht, F., Wetzel, M., Gudladt, H.-J., Hofmann, T., Meyer, J. C., Niedernhuber, M.: On the Fabrication and Automation of Reliable Bonded Composite Repairs, *The Journal of Adhesion*, DOI:10.1080/00218464.2014.896211, 5/2014